

MUHAMMAD ALI JINNAH'S VIEWS ON THE DIALOGUE BETWEEN EAST AND WEST: A PHILOSOPHICAL AND ANTHROPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of Muhammad Ali Jinnah's views on the problem of East-West interaction in the context of philosophical anthropology. It is shown that Jinnah combined elements of Western legal rationality and Eastern spiritual and cultural identity in his worldview, striving to integrate them into the project of Pakistani statehood. His concept proceeds from the idea of man as a being of a dual nature – a bearer of universal rights and a participant in a particular cultural tradition. The author proves that this is the philosophical and anthropological originality of Jinnah: he anticipates the modern idea of pluralistic modernization, which presupposes a dialogue of cultures without loss of their identity.

Keywords: Muhammad Ali Jinnah, East and West, philosophical anthropology, cultural identity, pluralistic modernization, postcolonial discourse.

The dialogue between East and West is one of the key themes in the history of modernization of non-Western societies. In the 20th century, against the background of the colonial crisis and the processes of decolonization, the problem of the correlation of Western universalist values and Eastern cultural traditions became particularly relevant. In this context, the figure of Muhammad Ali Jinnah, the founder of Pakistan and an outstanding political thinker, is of exceptional interest for philosophical and anthropological analysis. His views combine Western liberal legal concepts, which he learned during his studies in the UK, and a deep commitment to the Islamic civilizational tradition that shaped his identity as a political leader of the Muslims of the Indian subcontinent.

Jinnah completed his legal training at Lincoln's Inn (London) and was immersed in the Anglo-American tradition of common law. This left a noticeable imprint on his thinking: his speeches and documents clearly show the idea of individual rights and personal autonomy as the basis of a political order [1].

He consistently used the Western categorical grid: constitutionalism, parliamentary democracy, rule of law. However, it is characteristic that Jinnah did not absolutize the Western model, but viewed it as a tool rather than a goal.

His position is close to cultural pragmatism: borrowing Western institutions is justified only when they serve to protect the interests and identity of a particular people. Thus, Jinnah demonstrates the features of a cultural mediator, a figure located at the junction of civilizations and capable of connecting diverse value systems.

In parallel with the assimilation of Western legal thinking, Jinnah built the concept of cultural sovereignty of the Muslim community. In a 1940 speech in Lahore, he argued that India's Muslims are "not just a religious community, but a nation with its own culture, civilization, legal system, and historical identity" [2].

There is an anthropological argument here: a person is not thought of as an isolated individual, but as a carrier of historical and cultural identity. Hence Jinnah's key idea – the creation of a political order that would guarantee Muslims the opportunity to develop within their own civilizational matrix without dissolving into the Hindu majority. Thus, if Western law gave Jinnah the language of individual rights, then the eastern Islamic tradition gave him the image of a person as part of a community (ummah), where freedom is understood not only as autonomy, but also as loyalty to cultural roots.

Jinnah did not contrast East and West as mutually exclusive systems. In his discourse, they rather appear as two poles of human culture: rational-legal and spiritual-ethical. He proceeded from the fact that Western institutions of democracy and law can and should be adapted if they do not undermine the spiritual foundations of Eastern societies [3]. From an anthropological point of view, this means rejecting the Euro-centric model of "linear modernization" and recognizing the multiplicity of civilizational paths of development. Jinnah, in fact, offers a model of pluralistic modernity, in which cultural traditions are not eliminated, but become the basis for mastering the universal forms of modernity. This position is consistent with modern postcolonial theories that assert that modernization can occur without cultural westernization. In this regard, Jinnah can be considered as the forerunner of the ideas of "multipolar modernity" [4, 5].

Jinnah's ideas about the dialogue between East and West remain relevant in the context of globalization and cultural conflicts of the 21st century. His philosophical and anthropological attitude – the recognition of universal individual rights while preserving cultural identity – allows us to build models of inclusive modernization that take into account the specifics of non-Western societies.

For modern Pakistan, turning to Jinnah's philosophical legacy means finding a balance between Islamic identity and the need to integrate into the global system without losing cultural sovereignty.

Muhammad Ali Jinnah's views demonstrate an original approach to the problem of East-West interaction. In his philosophical and anthropological concept, man appears as a being of a dual nature – a bearer of universal rights and at the same time a product of a unique cultural environment.

It was this duality that became the basis for his project of Pakistani statehood: Jinnah sought to create not a copy of the Western state, but his own path combining rational institutions with spiritual values. This approach takes him beyond a purely political figure and makes him the subject of interest to philosophical anthropology as a thinker who proposed a model of intercivilizational synthesis.

References:

1. Jinnah, M. A. Speeches, Statements & Messages of the Quaid-e-Azam. Vol. 3. Lahore: Bazm-i-Iqbal, 1993.
2. Jalal A. The Sole Spokesman: Jinnah, the Muslim League and the Demand for Pakistan. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1985.
3. Malik I.H. Jinnah: Islam and the Creation of Pakistan. London: Routledge, 2000.
4. Parekh B. Gandhi's Political Philosophy: A Critical Examination. Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press, 1989.
5. Bhabha H. The Location of Culture. London: Routledge, 1994.

